

AN EVALUATIVE STUDY OF PUBLIC RELATIONS' PROMOTION OF NATIONAL VALUES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The pressing need to rebrand Nigeria's image and the general call for a deliberate change in global narratives and perceptions about Nigerians, regardless of their location worldwide, necessitated an evaluative study of Public Relations promotion of national values in Nigeria. The study examines the PR strategies deployed for the promotion of national values, the effectiveness of the strategies, and the likely campaign strategies that can be deployed for effective promotion of national values in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the Two-Way Symmetric Model, and a survey design method was adopted to provide answers to the study's claims. The findings revealed that limited campaign strategies were often deployed for public relations promotion of national values in Nigeria. This hindered the effectiveness of the efforts, which resulted in the demand for the deployment of multiple strategies such as grassroots participation, stakeholder collaboration, community partnerships, integration with education, public awareness, community engagement, school programmes, digital platforms, civil society partnership, role modeling, and influencer partnership, as against "jingle and slogans" commonly used. The study recommends that public relations practitioners should deploy various public relations strategies practicable for the promotion of national values and ensure that all public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria are effective through periodic evaluation and feedback, as well as introducing a feasible campaign that will integrate and accommodate all forms of strategies that can stimulate the promotion of national values in Nigeria.

Keyword: Public Relations, Evaluation, National Values, Campaigns, Strategies

Introduction

Public Relations (PR) plays a crucial role in shaping public perception and promoting values within a society. Nigeria, a country rich in cultural diversity and facing numerous socio-economic challenges, the promotion of national values through public relations campaign strategies has become increasingly important. Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa with over 237, 087 million people, has been grappling with issues of national identity and cohesion since its independence in 1960.

The country's diverse ethnic, religious, and linguistic landscape presents both opportunities and challenges for fostering a unified national ethos (NOA, 2025, Nwosu 2019). In recent years, the Nigerian government and various organisations have recognised the potential of Public Relations in addressing these challenges and promoting a sense of shared national identity. The concept of national values encompasses a wide range of principles and ideals that a country considers fundamental to its identity and progress.

In the Nigerian context, these values include unity, patriotism, integrity, discipline, social justice, religious tolerance, dignity of labour, and self-reliance (Okoye & Nwankwo, 2022). These values are essential for national development and social cohesion, particularly in a multicultural society like Nigeria.

This is the reason why many governmental agencies and organisations, such as National Orientation Agencies, NOA, Nigerians in Diaspora Commission, NIDCOM, Nigerian Institute of Public

Relations, NIPR, and others, have made it mandatory that every Nigerian must change their attitude and portray Nigeria in a good light in any country or continent they found themselves.

To this end, the Nigerian Institute of Public Relations is actively working to improve Nigeria's national reputation. On October 15th 2024, NIPR launched a Nigeria reputation brand, called Nigeria Reputation Management Group NRMG, with the sole objective of recognising the importance of public relations in shaping perceptions and collaborating with government agencies and other stakeholders to address negative narratives and promote a more positive image of Nigeria.

Recently, the National Orientation Agency (NOA) of Nigeria also embarked on national and international campaigns through "I'm A Real Nigeria" Jingle, Anthem and Slogans that aimed at changing the narratives tagged on anyone carrying "Green Passport" all over the world. The campaign was on the BBC, nation television, radio, internet and social media pop-up messages with the major intention of actively promoting a positive national narrative and patriotism through various means, including jingles, songs, and campaigns. One notable example is the "I'm A Real Nigeria" jingle, which is gaining popularity as a cultural phenomenon, encouraging a sense of national pride and civic responsibility amongst Nigerians, including children.

This jingle, along with other initiatives, is part of NOA's broader effort to shape a new generation of Nigerians who believe in the country's values and potential. They also came up with a slogan to change the derogatory phrases phrase. "Nigeria Has Happened To You" or "May Nigeria not Happen to You"; a common saying in Nigeria, reflecting a sense of cynicism and hardship, it is also used to convey the challenges and frustrations associated with living in Nigeria. Leveraging the potential of new digital technology (multimedia technologies), NOA also streams the slogan "Fall in Love with Nigeria" to help build the spirit of patriotism and nationality in Nigerians at home and abroad.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the public relations promoting of national values and the recognised importance of national values in fostering unity and development in Nigeria, there is a noticeable gap between the articulation of the values and the adaptation by the populace (Adekola, 2022). Several public relations campaign strategies aimed at promoting national values have been carried out in Nigeria through different public relations channels and programmes, yet its effectiveness remains questionable.

The problem may be linked to the disconnection between public relations' adoption of widespread reach campaign strategies and public attitudes towards national values. These disconnections of many scholars (Asemah et al., 2018; Olokesusi & Yusuf, 2019; Asemah et al., 2023, Nwaoboli & Emwinromwankhoe, 2024; Egbulefu & Nwaoboli, 2024) link to numerous factors such as; ethnic diversity, religious differences, and socio-economic disparities, bad governance and leadership, insecurity, poverty, discipline, and corruption.

Therefore, this study seeks to carry out an evaluative study of public relations promoting national values, considering the complexity and multi-dynamic nature of Nigeria's socio-cultural landscape.

In recognition of the above problem, the research provided answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria?
2. How effective are the public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria?
3. What are the likely public relations strategies that can be deployed for effective promotion of national values in Nigeria?

Literature Review

As the field of public relations continued to evolve, scholars and practitioners contributed to the development of theoretical frameworks and the effectiveness of public relations in promoting national values in Nigeria has been the subject of several empirical studies in recent years. Many of these studies look at various works done on the nature of public relations strategies, messages and campaigns in organisations and agencies. This study evaluates public relations promoting national values in Nigeria.

A study conducted by Arum et al., (2024) focused on the assessment of public relations practices of selected universities in Enugu State, Nigeria. The selected universities are University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu and Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu representing federal, state- and privately-owned universities respectively.

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The findings of the study revealed that the public relations unit plays a significant role in promoting the image of the selected universities. It was also found that the management gives fair support to public relations practices at the selected universities. The Public Relations unit is usually a party to all the decisions made; they are not only made to disseminate the information without making any input.

Similarly, Omachi, (2025) carried out a study to determine the public relations strategies of select local governments in Kogi State. The researcher sought to determine whether the public are satisfied with the public relations strategies of the local government areas; ascertain the influence of the public relations strategies on the image of the select local government areas; and identify the challenges faced by local governments in implementing their public relations strategies.

The study was premised on the situational theory of publics and the excellence theory of publics, which provided the theoretical foundation. The study utilised a mixed research design, incorporating both survey and interview. The findings of the study indicated that the select local government areas in Kogi State have a low frequency of use of public relations strategies. It recommended, amongst others, that local government authorities should take concrete steps to elevate the status and recognition of public relations within their organisations and create special departments for public relations practices so as not to be under the education departments.

Another study conducted by Adekoya (2022) assessed the effectiveness of public relations on the performance of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The result of the study revealed that public relations strategies have a significant impact on the performance of institutions of higher learning. The finding further showed that public relations units of institutions of higher learning play a small role in decision-making. The study concluded that public relations are indispensable in institutions of higher learning. To this end, the study recommended that public relations personnel of every institution of higher learning should be involved in decision-making and have free access to relevant information.

Meanwhile, Artem, (2022) has a look at PR-Message Analysis as a New Method for the Quantitative and Qualitative Communication Campaign Study. The study argued that communication practitioners often seek fast quantitative and qualitative analysis of the information campaign outcomes in the media space. The study explains that such analysis is required by PR departments of commercial brands, by political technologists, and by experts in information wars and ideology. A new approach for the analysis of information campaign outcomes is introduced in this paper.

Using PR messages as a category for analysis of media coverage of information campaigns provides a framework for credible efficiency evaluation, as well as for the deep analysis of the factors contributing to achievements or failures. This method allows the campaign organisers to understand what message it is better to disseminate in the media. In other words, through the messages of what kind the

opinion of the campaign initiator or their opponents is conveyed to the media audience more effectively. We consider a message to be a judgment in which an object or predicate relates to the substance of the information campaign.

Asemah-Ibrahim et al., (2022) evaluated the efficacy of Corporate Social Responsibility as a crisis management tactic for organisations. The objective of the study was to assess the efficacy of strategic Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the prevention and management of crises in organisations. The study employed the Uncertainty Reduction Theory as its theoretical framework. The study utilised a qualitative research method, which was suitable for examining a position paper.

The study suggests that the researchers found a correlation between effective utilisation of Corporate Social Responsibility and its potential for being highly feasible in crisis management. The data suggests that organisations possess a variety of Corporate Social Responsibility strategies that can be utilised to successfully prevent and manage crises. The incorporation of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in crisis prevention and mitigation strategies is crucial.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on a Two-Way Symmetric Model. The Two-Way Symmetric Model is a communication model within the field of public relations that emphasises the importance of balanced and reciprocal communication between organisations and their publics. The model originated from the work of James E. Grunig and Todd Hunt, who proposed it in their book "Managing Public Relations" (1984).

The Two-Way Symmetric Model is based on the idea that public relations should facilitate open and honest dialogue between organisations and their publics, aiming for mutual understanding and mutually beneficial outcomes (Arijeniwa, Nwaoboli, Ajimokunola & Uwuoruya, 2022, as cited in Jubrin, 2025). It challenges the traditional one-way communication approach that solely focuses on disseminating information and promoting organisational interests.

Instead, it promotes a two-way exchange of information, opinions and perspectives, where organisations listen to and engage with their publics in a genuine and respectful manner (Jubrin, 2025). The model encourages organisations to consider the needs and interests of their publics engage in active dialogue and make informed decisions that take into account the broader societal impact (Cutlip, Centre & Broom, 2006, as cited in Jubrin, 2025). The Two-Way Symmetric Model is relevant to this study because it emphasises the importance of open and honest dialogue between organisations and their publics.

In the context of the study, the government agencies, NIDCOM, NIPR and other nongovernmental organisations can use this model to assess the potential of public relations campaigns and promotion of national values in Nigeria. The Public Relations practitioners can use the two-way symmetric model to evaluate whether the messages and campaigns directed at moral and attitudinal change of Nigerians yielded any positive development. It will also explain the reasons most campaigns on promoting national values in Nigeria, and help to genuinely seek to engage in dialogue and understanding that will encourage Nigerians to trust and own the public relations campaigns for attitude change and patriotism.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design to evaluate the public relations promoting national values in Nigeria. This design was selected because of its ability to collect data from a large population efficiently and cost-effectively. The population for this study consisted of all residents of Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. According to the 2025 population projections, Minna had an estimated population of 532,497 residents.

This diverse population included individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds, age groups, and educational levels across different demographic segments within the Bosso and Chanchaga Local Government Areas in Minna. To determine an appropriate sample size for the study, Taro Yamane's formula was employed. This formula is widely used in social science research for calculating sample sizes from known populations. The formula is as follows: $N/n = (1 + N) (e)^2$, where: n = sample size, N = population size, e = Level of precision (assumed at 0.05 for this study). Calculation: $n = 399.69$.

Based on this calculation, the sample size was rounded up to 400 respondents to ensure adequate representation of the population of Minna. The study employed a simple random sampling technique to select respondents from the Bosso and Chanchaga Local Government Areas in Minna, the population of Minna. This probability sampling method was chosen for its fundamental characteristic of providing each participant with an equal and independent chance of being selected for the study.

The implementation of the sampling procedure followed a systematic and well-structured approach to ensure comprehensive coverage of the study area. Initially, Minna was stratified according to its existing administrative wards to guarantee geographical representation across the city. This preliminary stratification was essential in ensuring that the study captured the diverse socio-economic characteristics present across different areas of Minna, thereby enhancing the external validity of the research findings.

Findings and Discussion

Four hundred 400 copies of questionnaire were administered by the researcher to elicit data for the study, out of which 381 were retrieved and found useful.

Table 1: PR Strategies deployed for the Promotion of National Values in Nigeria

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Jingle and Slogans Campaigns Strategies	191	50.1%
Public Awareness Strategies	-	-
Community Engagement Strategies	-	-
School Programmes Strategies	19	5.0%
Digital Campaigns Strategies	143	37.5%
Civil Society Partnership Strategies	28	7.4%
Role Modeling Strategies	-	-
Influencer Partnership Strategies	-	-
Total	381	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 1, which sought to identify the public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria, shows that participants are only aware of jingles and slogans, campaign strategies, and digital campaign strategies. This indicates that Nigerians are only aware of a few public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria.

Table 2: How effective are the PR strategies deployed for the promoting of national values in Nigeria

Medium	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Effective	23	6.0%
Fairly	107	28.1%
Not Effective	251	65.9%
Total	389	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 2, which queries the effectiveness of public relations strategies deployed for the promoting of national values in Nigeria, indicates that the public relations deployed for the promoting of national values in Nigeria is not fairly effective. This implies that the public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria had no much impact on the intended audience.

Table 3: PR Strategies that can be deployed for effective promotion of national values in Nigeria

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Integration with education	381	100%
Youth engagement	373	98%
Grassroots participation	381	100%
Community partnerships	381	100%
Stakeholder collaboration	353	92.7%

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 3, which finds the likely public relations strategies that can be deployed for effective promotion of national values in Nigeria, shows that the majority of the participants suggested integration with education, grassroots participation, community partnerships, youth engagement and stakeholder collaboration as likely solutions to effective promotion of national values in Nigeria. This implies that there is need for deployment of more feasible public relations campaign strategies that can engender effective promotion of national values in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of an evaluative study of public relations' promotion of national values in Nigeria show that many efforts directed at changing the negative narrative about Nigerians and Nigeria as a nation by several government agencies, nongovernmental organisations, reputation and image promotion organisations such as; Nigerian Institute of Public Relations, Nigerians in Diaspora Commission and National Orientation Agencies as well as, media organisation have not yielded the intended desire, as many participants argued

that public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria are medium available to the elites in the urban areas in Nigeria. The majority of the participants were of the opinion that jingle and campaigns strategies and digital campaigns, which take the centre stage in the campaigns for the promotion of national values in Nigeria, are not out of place but lack a viable system for grassroots mobilisation.

This is the reason Egbulefu and Nwaoboli (2024) states that the impact of public relations campaigns is often limited by factors such as poor implementation, inadequate funding, and political interference. This also explains the reason many of the public relations campaign messages, such as: “Andrew, Don’t Check out,” “Change Begins with Me,” “I am a new Nigeria,” “Good People, Great Nation,” and many more are only echoed in the heart of the people who came in contact with it on radio, television and digital platforms; social media and major adverts applications.

James E. Grunig and Todd Hunt, in their book "Managing Public Relations" (1984), propose a Two-Way Symmetric Model which is based on the idea that public relations should facilitate open and honest dialogue between organisations and their publics, aiming for mutual understanding and mutually beneficial outcomes. This position revalidates the effectiveness of the PR strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria.

The majority of the participants affirmed that the campaign strategies are fairly effective and, in some cases, not effective at all. No wonder Adeniran and Nweke (2015) argue that many Public Relations campaigns fail to resonate with the diverse Nigerian populace due to a lack of cultural sensitivity and inadequate audience segmentation. This weak understanding of the effective way to inculcate and promote national values amongst Nigerians has caused a series of chaos, reputation damage and undermining the nation’s growth and development.

It has led to different ethnic groups that make up the nation and other countries in the world disparaging Nigeria's culture and values. To correct these irregularities and redirect all efforts towards building a nation with positive values and respect amongst the countries of the world, there is a need to ensure the integration of the core values, such as patriotism, truth, dignity, respect for national symbols and other philosophy, and allow adequate grassroots participation, community partnerships, youth engagement and stakeholder collaboration in the formulations, implementation and promotion of national values and patriotism amongst Nigerians irrespective where they reside.

These ideas are in line with the proponents of the Two-Way Symmetric Model, which proposes a more ethical and socially responsible approach to public relations. It argues that by engaging in open and transparent communication, organisations can build trust, enhance their reputation and foster positive relationships with their publics (Jubrin, 2025).

Corroborating the participants’ submissions, the National Orientation Agencies (NOA), in a publication titled: ‘The National Identity Projects’ concluded that PR communication campaign messages through slogans like “Building Nigerians to build Nigeria” which implies that to build Nigeria, Nigerians must build; we must build Nigerians to build Nigeria, “I serve ...to be served”; good governance and ‘Moving Nigeria to greatness’ unity are way forwards to changing Nigerians reputation all over the world (NOA, 2025). NOA also proposes discipline, transparency, integrity, good leadership and governance, tolerance and respect, duty of care, resilience and patriotism as ways effective promotion of national values can be imprinted on the heart of many Nigerians (NOA, 2025).

It suggests institutional policies such as nationalisation of cartoon animation on Nigeria's value content, integrating citizenship studies into the education curricula of children and young people within the age of 7 years and 22 years (NOA, 2025). The government should establish citizen brigades in Nigeria's primary and secondary schools. The agencies saddled with managing the global reputation management

campaign should carry a global reputation campaign outside Nigeria to promote values and redeem their image and good narrative about Nigerians all over the continent of the world.

Organising an orientation programme for the appointed and elected government officials, incorporation of value orientation as part of the National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) and Industrial Training Fund (ITF), as well as reintroduction of the promotion of National Symbols that can promote good identity, unity, pride as well as preservation of cultural heritage of Nigeria everywhere in the world (NOA, 2025). The Nigeria Institute of Public Relations, NIPR, launching Nigeria Reputation Management Group (NRMG) on October 15th, 2024, said sustainable strategies such as an annual reputation submit, a private sector approach, identifying critical national assets, public awareness, establishing reputation vanguards in all institutions will help rebuild Nigeria's reputation all over the world.

NIPR also builds the campaign strategies on seven (7) pillars; integrity, character, consistency, respect, trust, service delivery and rule of law (NIPR, 2024). This implies that public relations practitioners, government agencies, nongovernmental organisations, media and other reputation and value promotion organisations need to encourage and incorporate feedback actions and policies, in order to rebuild trust, credibility and sustainable values amongst Nigerians.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, there is no doubt that comprehensive strategies that accommodate strong support for educational integration, youth engagement, grassroots campaigns, digital engagement strategies, grassroots participation, stakeholder collaboration and engagement, as well as community partnerships can foster effective public relations' promotion of national values in Nigeria.

Thus, the need for a paradigm shift from the usual campaign strategy frequently deployed for public relations promotion of national values, such as slogans, jingles, anthems and digital messages, to a more robust and dynamic campaign strategies such as traditional media, digital platform engagement, influencers (traditional leaders and religious leaders), opinion moulders, using high quality of visual, video and infographics and storytelling to capture the interest of the intended audience, in order to inculcate the spirit of unity, tolerance, integrity, moral conducts, patriotism and positive global image in Nigerians who reside in the country and those in diasporas.

Recommendations

1. Public relations organisations should deploy various public relations strategies practicable for the promotion of national values in Nigeria.
2. Public Relations practitioners should ensure that all public relations strategies deployed for the promotion of national values in Nigeria are effective through periodic evaluation and feedback.
3. Public Relations practitioners should introduce a feasible campaign that will integrate and accommodate all forms of strategies that can stimulate the promotion of national values in Nigeria.

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